

EFFICACY OF INJECTION SECUKINUMAB IN ERYTHRODERMIC PSORIASIS

Dr. Maria Iqbal¹, Prof. Dr. Rabia Ghafoor², Rabia Baby³, Dr. Tarique Hussain⁴,
Dr. Bakhtawar Shaikh⁵

¹Resident FCPS Dermatology, JPMC

²Professor of Dermatology, JPMC

³Assistant Professor, Department of Education Sukkur IBA University

⁴JPMC

⁵Post-Fellowship Resident Psychiatry, LUMS Jamshoro

¹mariashaikh140@gmail.com, ²rabiaghafoordr@gmail.com, ³rabia.shaikh@iba-suk.edu.pk,

⁴tariksahto@gmail.com, ⁵shaikhbakhtawar7@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15589463>

Keywords

Secukinumab, erythrodermic Psoriasis, PASI Score.

Article History

Received on 26 April 2025

Accepted on 26 May 2025

Published on 04 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Dr. Maria Iqbal

Abstract

Objective: To determine the efficacy of Injection Secukinumab in erythrodermic Psoriasis (EP).

Methods: A total of 40 patients having EP were included. Patients with EP who completed the full treatment course of Injection Secukinumab were included. All participants in the study received a 300 mg subcutaneous injection of Secukinumab once a week for five weeks (specifically during weeks 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4). The Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) was assessed at several intervals, including weeks 0, 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20, alongside monitoring for any adverse drug reactions, patient satisfaction, and the frequency of recurrence.

Results: The participants in the study had an average age of 43.75 ± 10.98 years. Out of the 40 participants, there were 16 females (40%) and 24 males (60%). The typical duration for the current episode was approximately 1.24 ± 0.98 months, while the average duration of their disease spanned 3.60 ± 3.58 years. By the 4th week, this score had reduced to 26.63 ± 11.58 ; at the 8th week, it further declined to 18.17 ± 9.12 ; by the 12th week, it was at 12.37 ± 7.92 ; and by the 16th week, the average PASI score reached 10.30 ± 9.40 . In terms of treatment effectiveness, there was a marked increase in the percentage of patients who experienced a reduction of 75% or more in their PASI score from the baseline: 10% were noted at the 4th week, 40% at the 8th week, and 70% sustained this improvement from the 12th to the 20th week.

Conclusion: Secukinumab therapy is effective in treating patients with EP with minimal side effect profile and acceptable recurrence rates. So Secukinumab can be used as a preferred treatment option in EP patients.

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is a long-lasting inflammatory skin condition that affects approximately 2-3% of the global population.¹ While chronic plaque psoriasis is the most prevalent type, representing

over 80% of cases, there are various other clinical forms. One of the rarer and more severe types is erythrodermic psoriasis (EP), which occurs in less than 3% of individuals with psoriasis.² This

condition is marked by widespread scaling and redness, impacting more than 90% of the body's surface area.³ Because of the significant skin involvement, those with EP may experience a range of systemic symptoms, including chills, fever, itching, joint pain, dehydration, fatigue, and lymphadenopathy.⁴

The exact causes of EP remain poorly understood, which poses challenges for physicians in providing safe and effective treatment options. If left untreated, EP can result in significant mortality and morbidity due to acute skin failure. The breakdown of the skin's protective barrier increases the risk of secondary infections, while the loss of essential nutrients and proteins manifests as conditions such as anemia and hypoproteinemia.⁵

Secukinumab is a fully human monoclonal antibody that specifically targets and inhibits IL-17A, a key proinflammatory cytokine involved in psoriasis. By blocking the interaction between IL-17A and its receptor, secukinumab disrupts the inflammatory pathways associated with psoriasis, ultimately helping to restore normal immune responses and improve skin health. At the therapeutic doses used for treating psoriasis, it effectively neutralizes IL-17A without affecting IL-17F, ensuring that other Th17 functions and the Th1 immune response remain intact. This precise targeting may lead to fewer side effects compared to other systemic treatments currently on the market.^{6,8} The aim of this study was to determine the efficacy of Injection Secukinumab in Erythrodermic Psoriasis (EP).

METHODS:

Our longitudinal study describes patients with EP who visited the dermatology unit at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi from December 2024 to April 2025. We included patients who presented with clinical symptoms of EP, such as widespread redness and scaling covering over 90% of their body surface, and had histological evidence of psoriasis, with an age range of 18 to 65 years. The study was registered in clinical trial registry under trial number: NCT06801028.

Patients with EP who completed the full treatment course of Injection Secukinumab were included. Before starting Injection Secukinumab treatment, their medical history, physical examination, and lab results were evaluated to assess for infections, including hepatitis B and C, HIV, and tuberculosis (TB). This evaluation included complete blood count, C-reactive protein, liver function tests, kidney function tests, complete urinalysis, chest X-ray, PPD test, QuantiFERON-TB test, and tests for hepatitis B and C viral markers, HIV serology, and other relevant tests.

All participants in the study received a 300 mg subcutaneous injection of Secukinumab once a week for five weeks (specifically during weeks 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4). After this initial treatment phase, they switched to receiving the medication on a monthly basis. Follow-up evaluations were conducted every four weeks. The Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) was assessed at several intervals, including weeks 0, 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20, alongside monitoring for any adverse drug reactions, patient satisfaction, and the frequency of recurrence.

Demographic and clinical information was gathered, including age, gender, baseline PASI score prior to developing erythroderma (if applicable), prior anti-psoriatic treatment, exposure to biologic therapies, response to secukinumab, side effects, medication history, and PASI scores along with patient satisfaction assessments at weeks 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20. Efficacy was evaluated by monitoring changes in the PASI score from the initial assessment, with PASI-75 indicating treatment effectiveness. This was recorded following treatment initiation at weeks 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20. Additionally, adverse effects, recurrences, and reasons for discontinuation of secukinumab treatment were documented.

RESULTS:

The participants in the study had an average age of 43.75 ± 10.98 years. The mean Body Mass Index (BMI) was recorded at 26.61 ± 3.46 kg/m². Out of the 40 participants, there were 16 females (40%) and 24 males (60%). A significant portion, 18 individuals (45%), had previously undergone

systemic therapy, whereas none had received any biologic treatments. The typical duration for the current episode was approximately 1.24 ± 0.98 months, while the average duration of their disease spanned 3.60 ± 3.58 years. Regarding substance use, 6 participants (15%) indicated they were smokers, and 4 participants (10%) reported alcohol consumption. Furthermore, 12 individuals (30%) had been treated with methotrexate, and 4 (10%) had received phototherapy, but none had any history of using biologic therapies. Notably, all participants had not been exposed to biologic treatments before the study (Table 1).

The Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI) scores demonstrated notable improvements throughout the treatment period. Initially, the baseline average PASI score was recorded at 42.15 ± 13.82 . By the 4th week, this score had reduced to 26.63 ± 11.58 ; at the 8th week, it further declined to 18.17 ± 9.12 ; by the 12th week, it was at 12.37 ± 7.92 ; and by the 16th week, the average PASI score reached 10.30 ± 9.40 . Ultimately, a significant reduction was observed, with the score dropping to 7.85 ± 8.90 by the

20th week. In terms of treatment effectiveness, there was a marked increase in the percentage of patients who experienced a reduction of 75% or more in their PASI score from the baseline: 10% were noted at the 4th week, 40% at the 8th week, and 70% sustained this improvement from the 12th to the 20th week (Table 2).

Our track of adverse events over a 20-week duration revealed a notable increase in recurrence rates. Initially recorded at 0% during the 4th and 8th weeks, these rates increased to 25% by the study's conclusion. Candida infections were predominantly observed during the 4th week (25%) and 8th week (30%), while no cases were documented after the 12th week. At the 4th week, 15% of participants reported experiencing headaches, but these symptoms were absent in the following weeks. Additionally, upper respiratory tract infections (URTI) affected 20% of participants in the 4th week and 15% in the 8th week, with no further reports of URTI thereafter. Nasopharyngitis was noted in 10% of participants during the 4th week; however, no additional cases were found in the subsequent weeks (Table 3).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics.

Variable	Value
Age (Y)	43.75 ± 10.98
BMI (Kg/m ²)	26.61 ± 3.46
Gender (%)	
Female	16 (40%)
Male	24 (60%)
History of systemic therapy	18 (45%)
History of biologic therapy	0 (0.0%)
Duration of current episode (months)	1.24 ± 0.98
Duration of Disease (Years)	3.60 ± 3.58
Previous History of Addiction (%)	
Smoking	6 (15%)
Alcohol	4 (10%)
Pharmacological history (%)	
Methotrexate	12 (30%)
Phototherapy	4 (10%)
Adalimumab	0 (0.0%)
Etanercept	0 (0.0%)
Ustekinumab	0 (0.0%)
Biologics Navie	40 (100%)

Table 2. Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI) Score.

Mean PASI Score	
Baseline	42.15 ± 13.82
4 th -Week	26.63 ± 11.58
8 th -Week	18.17 ± 9.12
12 th -Week	12.37 ± 7.92
16 th -Week	10.30 ± 9.40
20 ^h -Week	7.85 ± 8.90
Efficacy (PASI score decrease 75.0% or more from Baseline)	
4 th -Week	04 (10%)
8 th -Week	16 (40%)
12 th -Week	28 (70%)
16 th -Week	28 (70%)
20 ^h -Week	28 (70%)

Table 3. Adverse Events.

Adverse events	4 th -Week	8 th -Week	12 th -Week	16 th -Week	20 th -Week
Recurrence	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (5.0%)	8 (20%)	10 (25%)
Candida infection	10 (25%)	12 (30%)	4 (10%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Headache	6 (15%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Upper respiratory tract infection (URTI)	8 (20%)	6 (15%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Nasopharyngitis	4 (10%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)

DISCUSSION:

EP is a complex inflammatory condition that can develop from pustular psoriasis or psoriasis vulgaris, often as a result of severe complications, infections, or inconsistent treatment practices. Managing erythrodermic psoriasis poses significant challenges due to the lack of standardized approaches, often leading to ineffective outcomes. Common systemic treatments that have been utilized for this condition include cyclosporine, methotrexate, oral retinoids, and systemic steroids. Unfortunately, the safety and effectiveness of these traditional therapies frequently fall short, with results being both unsatisfactory and unpredictable.^{9, 10} IL-17A plays a crucial role in the inflammatory cytokine response associated with psoriasis development. It activates keratinocytes, leading to increased cell proliferation, and stimulates the production of various cytokines, chemokines, and antimicrobial peptides, thereby exacerbating the inflammatory process.^{11, 12} Secukinumab, an IL-17A inhibitor, is known for its rapid effectiveness in clearing

lesions and achieving a 100% score on the Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI).¹³

In present study we determined the outcome of Secukinumab for treating EP, We achieved PASI score >75% in 70% patients at 20 weeks follow-up, while the recurrence rate was 25%.

Bhatnagar et al. in an observational study focused on patients with erythrodermic psoriasis who were successfully treated with secukinumab injections. The follow-up period spanned two years, during which the researchers monitored patient outcomes for recurrence and any adverse events. Remarkably, every patient displayed a successful response to the treatment. At week 4, 33.3% of patients exhibited a minimum 75% improvement in their Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) score, which further improved to 88.9% at week 12. Notably, none of the participants experienced a recurrence of the disease. These findings suggest that secukinumab is a rapid, safe, and effective treatment option for individuals suffering from psoriatic erythroderma.¹³

In a separate research study, patients diagnosed with erythrodermic psoriasis (EP) exhibited over 90% body surface area (BSA) involvement. They had an average baseline Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) score of 25.97 and an average Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI) score of 13.17. Remarkably, these patients were able to follow through with the complete therapeutic regimen for secukinumab, achieving a significant positive response and experiencing minimal side effects. Furthermore, they enjoyed prolonged periods of remission and expressed high levels of satisfaction with their treatment outcomes.¹⁴

A recent retrospective observational study conducted in India found that 75% of patients with plaque psoriasis achieved a PASI 75 score within just 4 weeks of treatment. Additionally, at the 12-week mark, the percentages of patients achieving PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 were 85%, 65%, and 10%, respectively. By the end of the 52-week period, 90% of patients maintained a PASI 75 score, while 50% achieved PASI 90 and 35% reached PASI 100. These findings highlight the rapid effectiveness of secukinumab in treating psoriasis, with the ability to sustain disease control over an extended duration.¹⁵

A comprehensive randomized placebo-controlled phase 3 study conducted in India by Bhat et al. examined the effectiveness and safety of secukinumab at doses of 300 mg and 150 mg, comparing the outcomes with Etanercept and a placebo. Notably, 61% of patients in the secukinumab 300 mg cohort and 55.9% in the 150 mg group achieved a 75% reduction in the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI 75), while only 20% of the Etanercept recipients and 7.1% of the placebo group reached this milestone. Additionally, 43.9% of the patients in the secukinumab 300 mg group and 20.6% in the 150 mg group demonstrated an Investigator's Global Assessment (IGA) score of 0 or 1 at week 12, in contrast to 13.3% in the Etanercept group and just 2.4% in the placebo cohort. The PASI 90 response rate was also significant, with 41.5% achieving this in the secukinumab 300 mg group and 20.6% in the 150 mg group, compared to 10% in the Etanercept group and none in the

placebo cohort. The researchers concluded that secukinumab was highly effective and well tolerated among participants in this study.¹⁶

This study highlights a significant finding: all patients exhibited a rapid reversal of erythroderma symptoms within few days after starting treatment. Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that Secukinumab is a safe and effective option for managing erythrodermic psoriasis, providing quick and reliable results.

CONCLUSION:

Secukinumab therapy is effective in treating patients with EP with minimal side effect profile and acceptable recurrence rates. So Secukinumab can be used as a preferred treatment option in EP patients.

REFERENCES

- 1.Griffiths CEM, Armstrong AW, Gudjonsson JE, Barker J. Psoriasis. *Lancet* (London, England). 2021;397(10281):1301-15.
- 2.Merola JF, Li T, Li WQ, Cho E, Qureshi AA. Prevalence of psoriasis phenotypes among men and women in the USA. *Clinical and experimental dermatology*. 2016;41(5):486-9.
- 3.Shao S, Wang G, Maverakis E, Gudjonsson JE. Targeted Treatment for Erythrodermic Psoriasis: Rationale and Recent Advances. *Drugs*. 2020;80(6):525-34.
- 4.Lo Y, Tsai TF. Updates on the Treatment of Erythrodermic Psoriasis. *Psoriasis* (Auckland, NZ). 2021;11:59-73.
- 5.Garner KK, Hoy KDS, Carpenter AM. Psoriasis: Recognition and Management Strategies. *American family physician*. 2023;108(6):562-73.
- 6.Krueger JG, Wharton KA, Jr., Schlitt T, Suprun M, Torene RI, Jiang X, et al. IL-17A inhibition by secukinumab induces early clinical, histopathologic, and molecular resolution of psoriasis. *The Journal of allergy and clinical immunology*. 2019;144(3):750-63.

7. Secukinumab. Drugs and Lactation Database (LactMed®). Bethesda (MD): National Institute of Child Health and Human Development; 2006.
8. Secukinumab. LiverTox: Clinical and Research Information on Drug-Induced Liver Injury. Bethesda (MD): National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases; 2012.
9. Reynolds KA, Pithadia DJ, Lee EB, Liao W, Wu JJ. A systematic review of treatment strategies for erythrodermic psoriasis. *The Journal of dermatological treatment.* 2021;32(1):49-55.
10. Carrasquillo OY, Pabón-Cartagena G, Falto-Aizpurua LA, Santiago-Vázquez M, Cancel-Artau KJ, Arias-Berrios G, et al. Treatment of erythrodermic psoriasis with biologics: A systematic review. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology.* 2020;83(1):151-8.
11. Galluzzo M, D'Adamio S, Campione E, Mazzilli S, Bianchi L, Talamonti M. A clinical case of severe disease burden: an erythrodermic psoriatic patient treated with secukinumab. *The Journal of dermatological treatment.* 2018:1-11.
12. Stinco G, Errichetti E. Erythrodermic psoriasis: current and future role of biologics. *BioDrugs : clinical immunotherapeutics, biopharmaceuticals and gene therapy.* 2015;29(2):91-101.
13. Bhatnagar A, Singh GK, Deshpande SK, Mitra B, Mitra D, Agrawal V, et al. Use of secukinumab in erythrodermic psoriasis: A single center experience. *Medical journal, Armed Forces India.* 2023;79(Suppl 1):S6-s12.
14. Panda M, Raj C, Panda AK, Debata I. Secukinumab in Erythrodermic Psoriasis: Real World Experience of 6 Patients Successfully Treated by Injecting at Unconventional Sites. *Indian journal of dermatology.* 2021;66(6):677-80.
15. Neema S, Radhakrishnan S, Singh S, Vasudevan B, Chatterjee MJJoDiD. Real-life efficacy and safety of secukinumab: A single-center, retrospective observational study with 52-week follow-up. 2019;5(1):14-8.
16. Bhat RM, Leelavathy B, Aradhya SS, Gopal MG, Pratap DV, Mubashir M, et al. Secukinumab efficacy and safety in indian patients with moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis: Sub-analysis from FIXTURE, a randomized, placebo-controlled, phase 3 study. *Indian dermatology online journal.* 2017;8(1):16-24.